

Parental Identity and Work–Parent Identity Integration in the Parental SkillScan

Empirical Findings and Methodological Implications for Assessment Efficiency

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The U-MICS-PI was used and evaluated in German with permission from its original author. Full item wording is not reproduced in this working paper. Internal PSS materials are clearly identified as developmental documents issued by the WorkFamily-Institut.

Abstract

This working paper examines the role of the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales for parental identity as part of the ongoing development of the Parental SkillScan (PSS). In an exploratory PSS development sample, reliability estimates, associations with Work–Parent Identity Integration (WPI/WPI5), and relationships with spillover expectation and reported use of parenting-related experiences at work were analyzed. The Piotrowski scales showed good to very good internal consistencies. WPI/WPI5 was associated with parental identity as expected, but contributed independently, particularly to SOEi, the instrumental work-related spillover expectation. Exploratory mediation models indicated indirect associations from commitment to SOEi via WPI/WPI5 and from WPI/WPI5 to SO-N via SOEi. The findings are consistent with a clear functional distinction: Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI remains important as a research module, whereas WPI5 remains part of the PSS standard version because of its conceptual fit, assessment efficiency, and practical utility. Due to the cross-sectional self-report design, the results are not to be interpreted causally.

Keywords: Parental SkillScan; parental identity; Work–Parent Identity Integration; Work–Family Enrichment; assessment efficiency; informal learning

Introduction

The Parental SkillScan (PSS) was developed to identify and articulate behavioral resources developed through parenting that can be transferred to work-related contexts. Its focus is not on a general evaluation of parenthood, nor on the attribution of stable traits solely on the basis of the parental role. Rather, the PSS conceptualizes parenthood as an informal learning environment in which individuals repeatedly address specific demands, reflect on their responses, and transfer what they have learned to other contexts.

During the development of the PSS, we examined whether an established measure of parental identity should be added to the existing measures of skills, spillover expectations, spillover use, recognition, and identity integration. Piotrowski’s U-MICS-PI was a natural candidate because it adapts the Utrecht-Management of Identity Commitments Scale to assess parental identity (Crocetti et al., 2010; Piotrowski, 2018). From a methodological perspective, there were initially compelling reasons for including it: the scale is theoretically grounded, differentiates among several identity processes, and assesses how the parental role is incorporated into the self-concept.

At the same time, questions of assessment efficiency and conceptual coherence arose: Does the full assessment of general parental identity provide sufficient added value for the PSS standard version, or would a more narrowly defined integration construct better serve its practical aims—one that directly connects the parental role with the work-related self-concept? The present working paper addresses this question through an empirically informed distinction between the constructs. Parental identity remains a relevant background construct; however, Work–Parent Identity Integration is more directly aligned with the PSS framework for transfer to work.

Theoretical Background

Parental Identity

Parental identity describes the extent and manner in which the parental role forms part of a person's self-concept. In the U-MICS-PI, this identification is conceptualized as a process and is represented by the dimensions commitment, in-depth exploration, and reconsideration of commitment (Piotrowski, 2018; Piotrowski et al., 2023). Commitment describes attachment to and commitment to the parental role, in-depth exploration describes deeper engagement with the parental role, and reconsideration describes the possible questioning or re-evaluation of parental role commitment.

This distinction is relevant to research in developmental, family, and identity psychology. It allows not only the assessment of whether parenthood is important, but also a differentiated view of whether parenthood is experienced as a stable part of the self-concept, actively reflected upon, or ambivalently questioned. For the PSS, however, a different question arises: the primary focus is not the general centrality of the parental role, but the transfer of behavioral resources developed through parenting to the workplace.

Work–Parent Identity Integration

Work–Parent Identity Integration refers to the subjective experience that the parental role and the work-related self-concept are not experienced as separate, contradictory, or competing identity domains, but rather as compatible and integrated aspects of the self. Whereas parental identity describes the importance of the parental role within the self-concept, WPI focuses on the interface between the parental role and work. In the literature on working parents, identity integration is discussed as a relevant variable for work-related, parental, and psychological outcomes (Manzi et al., 2022, 2024).

This interface is central to the logic of the PSS. A person may strongly identify with the parental role and nevertheless establish little connection between parenthood and competence development in the work context. Conversely, a person may not experience the parental role as a central component of identity and may still precisely recognize which parenting-related behavioral patterns are relevant at work. WPI/WPI5 therefore does not assess the intensity of general parental identity, but rather the integration process between the parental and work contexts.

PSS, SCOPE, and Work-Related Skill Articulation

The PSS framework is conceptually aligned with the work–family enrichment approach, which describes positive resource transfers between family and work roles (Carlson et al., 2006; Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). The SCOPE model represents five areas of parenting-related and work-relevant behavioral resources: S – self-leadership, C – Caring & Connection, O – providing orientation, P – enabling participation, and E – emotion regulation and communication. These areas are not understood as automatic consequences of parenthood, but as structured self-reports of behavioral patterns that can be consciously reflected on and articulated.

The core logic of the PSS is as follows: parenthood can be an informal learning context in which specific skills are practiced, stabilized, and differentiated. Whether these skills become relevant at work, however, does not depend solely on their possible existence. Their relevance depends on whether individuals

recognize and articulate these skills, relate them to work-related demands, apply them, and have them recognized within their organizational context.

Construct Distinction

The distinction between parental identity and Work–Parent Identity Integration is methodologically central. Parental identity answers the question of the salience, stability, active exploration, and possible ambivalence of the parental role within the self-concept. Work–Parent Identity Integration, by contrast, answers the question of whether the parental role and the work-related self-concept are experienced as compatible and capable of being integrated. The former concerns a broader identity-psychological construct, whereas the latter focuses specifically on transfer between parental and work roles and is more closely aligned with the practical purpose of the PSS standard version.

Research Questions

The present working paper is not intended as a broad validation study, but as a focused methodological development inquiry. The analyses inform decisions about how the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales should be used in future versions of the PSS. Four questions were central:

1. How are the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales related to WPI/WPI5?
2. Does parental identity explain work-related spillover expectation directly, or rather through perceived integration of parental and work identity?
3. Does WPI/WPI5 offer greater practical utility and assessment efficiency for PSS applications than the full assessment of general parental identity?
4. What consequences follow for the PSS standard version and for optional research or validation modules?

We hypothesized that parental identity would be a relevant background construct but not a sufficient direct indicator of work-related skill articulation or transfer expectations. For the PSS, WPI/WPI5 is the more appropriate identity construct because it more directly captures the integration process between the parental role and the work-related self-concept.

Method

Sample

The analyses support the ongoing methodological development of the PSS and do not constitute a definitive external validation of the German-language Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI version. Because the measures were administered at different stages and were not available for all participants, analytic sample sizes varied across models. For the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales and WPI, complete data were available from $N = 212$ participants; for WPI5, $N = 117$ cases were available. For the models involving SOE, SOEi, SOEe, SOEa, and SO-N, each model included all cases with complete data for the variables analyzed. The present analyses should therefore be interpreted as an exploratory evaluation of the German-language study version as part of PSS development.

Instruments

The U-MICS-PI was used in a German study version.¹ The original author authorized both the use of the scale and the evaluation of a German-language version. According to the author, no German-language version was available at the time of the request. The present analyses are therefore to be understood as an exploratory examination of the German study version as part of PSS development. Full item wording is not reproduced in this working paper.

WPI/WPI5. WPI/WPI5 assesses perceived integration of the parental role and the work-related self-concept. Within the PSS, the scale is intended as a brief and efficient measure of identity integration and is designed to capture whether parenthood and work are experienced as compatible roles and as capable of being coherently integrated into the self-concept.

SCOPE. The SCOPE model represents five skill areas: self-leadership, Caring & Connection, providing orientation, enabling participation, and emotion regulation and communication. The scales are based on standardized self-reports and are scored and interpreted within the PSS using a reference-based framework.

SOE, SO-N, and SO-A. SOE assesses the expectation of positive spillover effects, differentiated into SOEe, SOEi, and SOEa. SO-N describes the reported use of skills acquired through parenthood in the work context. SO-A was considered conceptually, but it was not analyzed as extensively as SO-N in the present study.

Statistical Analyses

Reported analyses include reliability analyses using Cronbach's α and McDonald's ω , Pearson correlations, linear regressions, hierarchical regressions, and exploratory mediation models with bias-corrected bootstrap confidence intervals. All analyses are to be interpreted as exploratory. The cross-sectional self-report data do not support causal inference. The findings primarily inform the further development of the PSS standard version.

Results

Descriptive Statistics and Reliabilities

The reliability analyses yielded good to very good internal consistencies for the three Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales (Table 1). WPI5 also achieved adequate reliability for the intended short scale with five items. Thus, the decision not to include the Piotrowski scales in the PSS standard version is not attributable to poor psychometric performance.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Reliabilities of the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI Scales and WPI/WPI5

Scale	N	Items	M	SD	α	ω
Commitment	212	5	3.35	0.906	.887	.888
In-depth Exploration	212	5	3.71	0.819	.842	.849

¹ We thank Prof. Dr. Konrad Piotrowski for granting permission to use the U-MICS-PI and for noting that, at the time of the request, no German version was known to be available.

Reconsideration of Commitment	212	3	1.66	0.880	.873	.889
WPI, 4 items	212	4	3.38	0.781	.720	.732
WPI+	117	6	3.31	0.733	.781	.787
WPI5 / WPI+(5)	117	5	3.38	0.782	.783	.788

Note. α = Cronbach's alpha; ω = McDonald's omega; WPI = Work-Parent Identity Integration. Sample sizes vary because not all measures were available for all participants.

Correlations Between Parental Identity and WPI/WPI5

The correlations show the expected relationship between parental identity and WPI/WPI5, without equating the constructs (Table 2). Commitment was most strongly and positively associated with WPI and WPI5, whereas reconsideration was negatively associated with both integration measures. WPI5 correlated very highly with WPI, supporting WPI5 as an efficient short-form measure of the integration construct.

Table 2
Correlations Between Parental Identity and WPI/WPI5

Association	r	p	N
Commitment – WPI	.468	< .001	212
In-depth Exploration – WPI	.203	.003	212
Reconsideration – WPI	-.303	< .001	212
Commitment – WPI5	.433	< .001	117
In-depth Exploration – WPI5	.230	.013	117
Reconsideration – WPI5	-.272	.003	117
WPI – WPI5	.977	< .001	117

Note. WPI5 = WPI+(5). Negative signs indicate inverse associations.

Associations With SOE Dimensions

The associations with SOEtotal, SOEe, and SOEi show distinct patterns (Table 3). Commitment was particularly strongly associated with SOEe and SOEtotal. WPI also showed substantial associations with the SOE dimensions and was particularly relevant for SOEi, the instrumental work-related spillover expectation. Reconsideration was negatively associated with the SOE dimensions, as expected.

Table 3
Correlations With SOEtotal, SOEe, and SOEi

Predictor	SOEtotal r	SOEe r	SOEi r
Commitment	.603***	.605***	.455***
In-depth Exploration	.278***	.234**	.208**
Reconsideration	-.448***	-.515***	-.279***
WPI	.456***	.369***	.408***

Note. **p < .01. ***p < .001. SOEe = general parenting-related spillover expectation; SOEi = instrumental or identity-related work-related spillover expectation.

Regression Models for SOEtotal, SOEe, and SOEi

In the regression models, SOEe showed a different pattern than SOEi (Table 4). SOEe was explained primarily by commitment and reconsideration; WPI did not make an independent contribution here. For SOEi, by contrast, both commitment and WPI accounted for unique variance. This supports the assumption that WPI/WPI5 is particularly relevant to the PSS framework for transfer to work.

Table 4*Regression Models Predicting SOEtotal, SOEe, and SOEi*

Criterion	N	R	R ²	Predictor	b	p
SOEtotal	180	.648	.420	Commitment	0.315	< .001
				Reconsideration	-0.147	.008
				WPI	0.169	.005
SOEe	194	.660	.436	Commitment	0.440	< .001
				Reconsideration	-0.299	< .001
				WPI	0.071	.356
SOEi	191	.508	.258	Commitment	0.237	< .001
				Reconsideration	-0.043	.464
				WPI	0.220	< .001

Note. b = unstandardized regression coefficient. All models included commitment, reconsideration, and WPI simultaneously. The corresponding models with WPI5 showed a comparable pattern. For SOEtotal, WPI5 was significant (b = 0.195, p = .012, R² = .424, N = 98). For SOEe, WPI5 was not significant (b = 0.136, p = .203, R² = .457, N = 106). For SOEi, WPI5 made an independent contribution (b = 0.220, p = .008, R² = .271, N = 105).

Exploratory Mediation Models

The exploratory mediation models were consistent with a statistical mediating role for WPI/WPI5 (Table 5). The indirect effect of commitment on SOEi via WPI was significant; the same was true for the corresponding model with WPI5. Because the direct effects remained significant in each case, these are partial mediations. Additional models for SO-N showed that WPI/WPI5 was associated with the reported use of parenting-related experiences at work via SOEi.

Table 5*Exploratory Mediation Models*

Model	N	Indirect effect b	SE	95% CI	β	p	Classification
Commitment → WPI → SOEi	191	0.088	0.028	[0.039, 0.145]	.117	.001	partial
Commitment → WPI5 → SOEi	105	0.082	0.034	[0.023, 0.157]	.115	.015	partial
WPI → SOEi → SO-N	172	0.182	0.043	[0.089, 0.289]	.199	< .001	indirect
WPI5 → SOEi → SO-N	96	0.212	0.056	[0.107, 0.363]	.227	< .001	indirect

Note. The mediation analyses are based on cross-sectional self-report data and are to be interpreted as exploratory, not causal. CI = confidence interval.

A supplementary model with SOEi and SOEe as predictors of SO-N yielded R = .586 and R² = .344 with N = 358. SOEi was a strong predictor of SO-N (b = 0.703, p < .001), whereas SOEe made no independent contribution when SOEi was considered simultaneously (b = -0.003, p = .939). Thus, instrumental work-related spillover expectation is more closely associated with reported use than general parenting-related spillover expectation.

Incremental Contribution of SCOPE in Hierarchical Models

The hierarchical models show that SCOPE complements the identity logic (Table 6). For SOEi and SOEtotal, adding the SCOPE areas increased the explained variance. In particular, S – self-leadership emerged as a relevant additional predictor. For SOEa, by contrast, no meaningful incremental contribution of the SCOPE areas was found.

Table 6*Hierarchical Regression Models Showing the Incremental Contribution of SCOPE*

Criterion	Model 1 R ²	Model 2 R ²	ΔR ²	p for ΔR ²	Relevant predictors in the extended model
SOEi	.258	.318	.060	.008	Commitment, WPI, S – self-leadership
SOEtotal	.420	.490	.070	< .001	Commitment, reconsideration, WPI, S – self-leadership
SOEe	.436	.487	.051	.003	Commitment, reconsideration, C – Caring & Connection
SOEa	.405	.414	.009	.732	no meaningful incremental contribution of SCOPE

Note. Model 1 included commitment, reconsideration, and WPI. Model 2 added the five SCOPE areas S, C, O, P, and E.

Summary Interpretation of the Findings

Overall, the results support a clear functional distinction. The Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales provide a reliable and differentiated assessment of parental identity. WPI/WPI5 is associated with this parental identity as expected, but captures the PSS-specific interface between the parental role and the work-related self-concept. In particular, the findings on SOEi and SO-N support retaining WPI5 as a standard module of the PSS and retaining Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI as an optional research module.

Discussion

Psychometric Interpretation of the Piotrowski Scales

In the present PSS development sample, the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales show good to very good internal consistencies. The decision not to include the scales in the PSS standard version is therefore not based on insufficient scale quality. On the contrary, the findings suggest that the study version used here reliably captures the three parental identity processes. Its function, however, lies primarily in the domain of research and construct validation, rather than in routine PSS use.

Construct Distinction Between Parental Identity and WPI/WPI5

The correlations show expected associations between parental identity and WPI/WPI5, but do not support equating the constructs. Commitment was positively associated with WPI/WPI5, whereas reconsideration was negatively associated. This pattern is theoretically plausible: individuals who experience stronger commitment to the parental role may be more likely to integrate this role into their work-related self-concept; individuals who more strongly question their parental role commitment tend to report lower levels of integration. Nevertheless, WPI/WPI5 addresses a more specific question: the compatibility and integration of the parental role and the work-related self-concept.

Different Patterns for SOEe and SOEi

The results distinguish between a general positive expectation derived from parenthood and instrumental work-related spillover expectation. SOEe was explained primarily by commitment and reconsideration. WPI/WPI5 was not uniquely associated with SOEe. For SOEi, by contrast, a different pattern emerged: in addition to commitment, WPI and WPI5 made independent contributions. This is theoretically consistent because SOEi captures work-related transfer expectation and is therefore more directly aligned with the integration of parental and work identities.

WPI/WPI5 as a Bridge Construct

The exploratory mediation models are consistent with a bridge function of WPI/WPI5. Commitment was associated with SOEi not only directly, but also indirectly via WPI and WPI5. In addition, WPI/WPI5

was associated with SO-N, the reported use of parenting-related experiences at work, via SOEi. These findings suggest that WPI5 is not merely another identity measure for the PSS, but a practice-oriented construct that captures the interface between parental role commitment, work-related spillover expectation, and reported use.

SCOPE as a Complementary Skill Dimension

SCOPE complements the identity logic. In particular, S – self-leadership explained additional variance in SOEi and SOEtotal beyond commitment, reconsideration, and WPI. This supports the PSS assumption of two complementary pathways: an identity pathway via WPI/WPI5 and a skills pathway via the self-reported SCOPE resources. For practical PSS interpretation, this combination is particularly useful: WPI5 captures identity integration, while SCOPE describes the specific behavioral resources that respondents can identify and articulate.

Methodological Implications for the PSS

The empirical findings support a clear functional distinction. The Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales assess general parental identity reliably and differentially. For the PSS standard version, however, WPI5 is the more appropriate identity construct because it captures the interface between the parental role and the work-related self-concept, which is central to the PSS, more efficiently. WPI5 shows sufficient internal consistency, strong convergence with the full WPI measure, and relevant associations with SOEi and SO-N. The Piotrowski scales are therefore not excluded because of substantive or psychometric weaknesses; instead, they are retained as an optional research module to keep the standard version focused, application-oriented, and efficient.

Table 7

Decision Matrix for the PSS Standard Version

Decision dimension	Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI	WPI5	Consequence
Reliability	good to very good	acceptable to good	both usable
Construct focus	general parental identity	integration of parental role × work	WPI5 closer to the PSS core
Assessment efficiency	several subscales, higher number of items	five items	WPI5 more efficient
SOEi relevance	commitment relevant	independently relevant	retain WPI5
SO-N relevance	less directly examined	direct and indirect relation via SOEi	WPI5 closer to application
Standard version	do not include	include	clear functional distinction
Research module	yes	yes, but part of the standard version	Piotrowski optional

Note. The decision concerns the PSS standard version. For research questions on parental identity, the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales remain relevant.

Limitations

These findings should be interpreted as exploratory analyses conducted during instrument development. The cross-sectional self-report data do not support causal conclusions, particularly regarding the mediation models. Analytic sample sizes varied across models; the sample size is reported separately for each model. In addition, there is no external replication in an independent sample.

A further limitation concerns the German study version of the Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI scales. The U-MICS-PI was used in a German study version with permission from the author. Full item wording is not

published in this working paper. The present findings should be interpreted as an exploratory evaluation of this study version as part of PSS development. SO-A was not documented as extensively as SO-N in the available dataset and was therefore not reported numerically. Based on the present findings, WPI5 is attractive as a brief and efficient measure, but should be replicated in further samples and application contexts.

Conclusion

The findings do not call the Piotrowski measure into question; instead, they support a clearer functional distinction. Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI assesses general parental identity, whereas WPI5 captures the PSS-relevant integration of parental and work identities. The PSS standard version therefore retains WPI5, while Piotrowski/U-MICS-PI remains available as an optional research module.

This decision does not devalue parental identity as a construct; rather, it represents a methodological refinement. The PSS does not seek to provide a comprehensive assessment of parental identity. Instead, it aims to identify and articulate parenting-related skills and support their integration and use at work. WPI5 captures this core function more directly and efficiently than a comprehensive measure of general parental identity would.

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